

Preservation of Library Materials in Indian Libraries

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Abstract

The intellectual heritage of our country is stored and preserved in our libraries. Libraries collect, store and preserve books, manuscripts, newspapers, historical documents and other important archival materials. Being organic in nature, these library materials are threatened by different agents of deterioration. Physical, chemical and biological agents damage library materials in various ways. Several conservation techniques and methods are adopted by the libraries in India to prevent and halt the deterioration of library materials housed in different libraries. This article focuses on the different agents of deterioration and the techniques of conservation of library materials. It also highlighted the conservation practices adopted in different libraries in India.

Key words: Deterioration, Preservation, Conservation, Library Materials, Libraries.

Introduction

People express their thoughts through speech and writing. Ancient people expressed their ideas and observations through various cave paintings and rock art. Gradually, the writing skill had been developed among societies and the clay tablet, inscriptions on stone, copper, gold or other materials came into existence. Organic material came into use, and the practice of manuscript writing became popular. With time and the advent of societies, books came into existence. These manuscripts, books and all other written forms of knowledge have been stored in libraries since time immemorial. Hence, libraries are our storehouse of knowledge and intellectual heritage. Libraries store and preserve our thoughts, facts, ideas and records of human civilization.

Material composition of Library collections

Library materials include collections and storage or repository of books, documents, maps, letters, newspapers, manuscripts and other important documents. All these materials are organic in nature. Books and other documents are made of paper whereas manuscripts are made of palm leaf, birch bark, sanchipat, parchment, paper, cloth, etc. Maps can also be of paper or parchment. Paper documents can be prepared from machine-made or handmade paper. Being organic in nature, library materials are susceptible to damage. Various damaging factors are responsible for the deterioration of library materials.

Causes of Deterioration

The major causes of deterioration and damage of library materials can be divided into three categories – physical, chemical and biological. These major categories can further be subdivided into several subcategories.

Physical factors:

It includes various natural disasters and calamities along with fundamental activity, terrorist activity and armed conflict in a region. Natural disasters like cyclones, floods, landslides, earthquakes, etc., are very common in the Indian subcontinent. Cyclone is a common phenomenon in the coastal states of India. Every year, a huge number of properties are damaged due to cyclonic storms over the Bay of Bengal or the Arabian Sea. Flood is a common disaster in India. Every year, many parts of the country are flooded due to heavy rain. Waterlogging causes damage to library materials of libraries in flooded areas. The floods in Chennai in 2016 caused severe damage to library collections. In the Cochin House Library, more than 1500 books were damaged during the flood (The Hindu, 24.03.2026). In Bhasa Bhawan, National Library, Kolkata, several books, periodicals were damaged because of water leaking from the air-conditioning plant, and rainwater was pouring through a broken window (Times of India, 13.07.2016). Armed conflict and fundamental activities often destroy the library collections. During a riot in Bihar Sharif in 2023, a 113-year-old madrasa library was torched. The library housed more than 4,500 books, including ancient manuscripts, calligraphy and ancient Islamic texts. All turned to ash (BBC, 23.04.2023).

Chemical factors:

Chemical factors can be divided into the following sub-categories.

Climate:

Relative humidity and temperature are two main components of climate. They are interrelated. The increase and decrease of humidity and temperature within a confined area damages the library materials of library. If the temperature increases, the humidity of organic documents evaporates and becomes dry. As a result, organic materials, especially paper documents and parchment, become brittle. Excessive humidity causes dampness and promotes fungal growth and other microbial activity.

Light:

The sun is the only source of natural light in libraries. Artificial lights are used in libraries to illuminate the rooms. Natural and artificial, both are great threats to library materials. “Light is main factor of colour fading of the illustrated and illuminated manuscripts” (Kharbade, 2005:23). The extent of illumination and duration of exposure control the damage of library materials.

Material composition:

Sometimes material composition of the library material itself becomes a deteriorating agent. Such as paper made with an amalgamation of different fibrous and sizing materials, which can damage the paper in the future. Sizing materials added to the paper during manufacturing can cause acidity. Ink contains sulphur as an ingredient, reacts with atmospheric gases and turns to sulphuric acid, which accelerates the weakening of paper (Singh, 1987).

Biological factors:

The climatic conditions of India are favourable for biological activity. Microbial activity increases when the temperature crosses 30°C and the relative humidity touches 70% (Biswas, 2024). Insects are the most damaging factor for library materials. Silverfish, book lice, bookworms, cockroaches, termites, etc., eat the leaves of manuscripts and books. They also eat binding glue and create holes or tunnels on leaves of books, manuscripts and other documents. Rats, birds, etc. are also destroy library materials. Human is a great threat to library materials as their mishandling and negligence often damage library materials in libraries. Sometimes people intentionally damage the library collection. It can be called ‘Malpractice’.

Conservation and Preservation

There are various conservation techniques for library materials. They are-

- Preventive conservation
- Curative conservation
- Restoration/ Mending/ Repair (Jeyaraj, 2007)

Preventive conservation

Preventive conservation is termed as the indirect actions taken to increase the life expectancy of library materials and prevent further damage. Preventive conservation is done by controlling the factors of deterioration. Climate control, control of illumination of light, storage maintenance, proper handling, and regular cleaning in library premises, etc., reduce the chance of damage in a library. UV filters can be used to filter the artificial lights in libraries. For controlling humidity and temperature air conditioning method can be used, but it should run for 24 hrs every day.

The ideal temperature and R.H. in the stack room is 21°C – 25°C and 45 – 60% ideal R.H. The above ideal temperature and relative humidity control the growth of fungi and insects. Periodical inspection, dust removal and keeping insect repellents control

the insects. If there are insect-affected materials, they should be immediately fumigated with paradichlorobenzene (Perumal,2002:55).

The librarians must know the deterioration factors responsible for the damage and should take measures according to them to prevent further damage.

Several preventive methods can be adopted to prevent further damage.

- Temperature should be kept between 18°C and 24°C.
- Relative humidity should be maintained between 45% and 55%.
- Illumination of light should be maintained below 50 LUX.
- The light should be turned off if there is no one in the storage.
- Gloves should be used during handling.
- Writing on library materials should be prohibited.
- Regular inspection should be carried out on insect infestation.
- Training should be provided to the library staff for handling the library materials.
- Water pipe line and electrical line should be outside the storage to prevent accidental damage.
- No food, drinks or smoking should be allowed in the vicinity of library materials.

Curative conservation

Curative conservation is the direct action taken to halt the deterioration of library materials. Curative conservation is done in different steps. They are discussed below.

Cleaning:

Cleaning can be done in a mechanical process (i.e., without using chemicals) or solvent cleaning. Mechanical cleaning can be done by using a soft brush, swab stick, spatula, etc. Dust from manuscript leaves is removed by dry brush cleaning.

Fumigation:

To eradicate live insect and/or fungal infestation, fumigation is done. Library materials are kept on the perforated shelves inside a concealed chamber, called a fumigation chamber, for 7 to 15 days, depending on the infestation. Fumigants are used to fumigate the materials. A 60-watt bulb is installed inside the chamber. The bulb remains switched on for two hours every day to heat the chemicals. The chemicals vaporised and the fumes travelled through the folios of manuscripts and pages of books and documents.

De-acidification of paper:

De-acidification is the treatment of acidic paper. Acidic paper can be de-acidified in two ways: the dry and wet methods.

Before the de-acidification of the paper, the ink of the paper is tested. If the ink is dissolved in water, dry de-acidification is done. Papers with water-soluble ink are treated in non non-aqueous method.

The paper which is to be treated should be kept between a nylon or terylene net, and then immersed in a tub containing a solution of calcium hydroxide and subsequently in calcium bicarbonate solution to make it acid-free (Sing, 1987:79).

If the paper is written with permanent ink, wet de-acidification can be carried out. Saturated lime water is used in the aqueous method of de-acidification. Lime water reacts with carbon dioxide and forms calcium carbonate, which neutralises acidity (Jeyaraj, 2002). A saturated solution of barium hydroxide in methanol can be used for non-aqueous de-acidification of paper materials.

Reinforcement:

Reinforcement of both paper material and palm leaf manuscripts is done. In case of fragile paper, Japanese or Nepalese tissue paper is used to give support. To reintegrate the broken or missing parts of palm leaf manuscripts, seasoned palm leaves are used. The new leaves are cut according to the missing part and added to the leaf to prevent further breakage. At the first step of reinforcement seasoned palm leaf is selected to cut. The colour of the chosen folio should be the same as the old folio as far as possible. Then the new folio is cut according to the missing part and added with a suitable adhesive.

Tunnel filling:

Insects create tunnels on palm leaves by eating them. These tunnels are filled to prevent further damage. Generally, fibres of Nepalese tissue paper are used to fill the tunnels and holes created by insects.

Digitization:

Now we are living in a digital era. Digital technologies have opened a new window to the conservation of library materials. Nowadays, libraries and archives are digitizing their existing resources. According to the National Mission for Manuscripts (NMM), “Digitization means acquiring, converting, storing and providing information in digital format that is standardized, organized and available on demand” (Guidelines for Digitization of Library Material, n.d:20). Microfilm is also used to preserve a digital copy of library materials. Digitization reduces the use and handling of physical copies of library materials. It helps to preserve the documents. The digitized copy is generally stored in hard discs, CDs, DVDs, pen drives, microchips chip etc. In recent times, libraries are storing their digitized copy in Cloud Storage. The National Mission for Manuscripts (NAMAMI) was launched in 2003. This mission is dedicated to the documentation, conservation, and digitization of India's vast manuscript heritage. It has been a major force in creating a digital library of manuscripts, with a target to digitize millions of folios. This mission has recently been restructured as the Gyan Bharatam Mission for 2024-2031, with a significant budget allocation to continue and expand these efforts. The National Digital Library of India (NDLI) is a project to create a national repository of digital learning resources, integrating content from various sources, including institutional repositories, to provide a single-window platform for all learners.

Conservation Practices followed in Indian Libraries

Indian libraries follow both the preventive and curative treatment. Non-chemical treatment using indigenous material is also popular among libraries to eradicate biological deteriorating agents.

Regular cleaning of manuscripts with a soft brush and a vacuum cleaner is done in the Asiatic Society, Kolkata. They stored manuscripts after wrapping them with acid-free paper or red cotton cloth to protect them from dust and insects. The Asiatic Society controls the microclimate to prevent damage.

Humidity beyond 70% permits moulds to grow and flourish. It causes the paper to swell and the pigment layer to peel off. So, temperature 22°C to 24°C and relative humidity at 55% to 60% have been controlled by 24-hour air conditioning system in the stack area of the Society (Das, 2006:161).

Chemicals like Silica Gel and Calcium Chloride are also in use to control humidity in Society. Indigenous materials like dried neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf, sandalwood (*Santalum album*), tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) leaves, etc., are used to control biological agents.

Manuscripts in Saraswati Mahal Library, Thanjavur, have been treated with turmeric paste to repel insects. Saraswati Mahal Library uses a mixture of indigenous material in its powder form as an insect repellent. The powder is kept within a cloth sachet inside the storage box or almirah. Perumal (2006:173) has given the components of the mixture.

Ingredient	Quantity
Black cumin	4 parts (1 kg)
Sweet flag	4 parts (1 kg)
Cloves	1 part (¼ kg)
Pepper	1 part (¼ kg)
Bark of cinnamon	4 parts (1 kg)
Camphor	20 grams

Books and manuscripts attacked by insects are kept in a separate almirah in Rampur Raza Library, Rampur, Uttar Pradesh. Library materials are taken out from the almirah, and the folios of manuscripts and pages of books are cleaned manually by a soft brush. Brittle and damaged books

are repaired and mended. Illustrated damage manuscripts have also been repaired using maida paste mixed with powder of copper sulphate and a mixture of alum (Siddiqui, 2006).

The repository and libraries of Manipur use different indigenous techniques to preserve books and manuscripts. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf, tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) leaf, marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) leaf, tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) leaf, etc., are popular indigenous materials in Manipur. For preserving the writing materials from insects and worms, the writing materials are dipped in cow urine for 5 to 6 hours (Sushila Devi, 2006).

Khuda Bakhs Oriental Library, Patna, uses different techniques for preserving library materials. The techniques include – preventive conservation, curative conservation, microfilming and digitization of library materials (Moid et. al, 2023). Dust removal, fumigation, de-acidification of paper materials, and reinforcement of fragile paper documents are the curative treatments carried on for library materials in the library.

The libraries have a disaster management system to prevent damage caused by disasters. Fire safety measures like installation of fire extinguishers, smoke or fire detectors, sand buckets, etc., are major preventive measures for fire disasters.

Conclusion

Libraries are the repository of intellectual heritage. Modern libraries of India contain both the traditional and digital media of conservation techniques. In this digital era, most of the books and manuscripts are being digitized by various institutions for easy access and preserving the physical copy for the future. Digitization reduces the need for large physical storage spaces, which are expensive to maintain and secure. It also lowers the long-term costs associated with physical preservation, such as climate control, pest management, and manual repair. Different libraries

follow different conservation methods to preserve the library materials. Alongside the curative and preventive techniques of conservation, indigenous methods are also very popular for preservation. By combining traditional conservation wisdom with modern technology like digitization, we can create a powerful approach. Ultimately, preserving library materials is a shared responsibility. It requires a sustained commitment from policymakers to provide funding, from librarians to implement best practices, and from the public to understand the value of these treasures. By doing so, we can ensure that our nation's history and knowledge endure, ready to enlighten future generations and stand as a testament to our rich and enduring civilization.

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